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Kohinoor Business School
Center for Management Research, Khandala

PURCHASE DECISIONS: AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF WOMEN'S ROLE IN FAMILY

Prof. Atul Kumar

Faculty Member, Department of Management,
Siddhant College of Engineering, Pune, Maharashtra
Email: atulk.singh@yahoo.co.in

Dr. (Mrs.) Vinaydeep

Faculty Member
Siddhant Institute of Business Management, Pune, Maharashtra
Email: atul_adroit@rediffmail.com

Abstract:

The purpose of this paper was to analyze the relationship between demographic and geographic variables of women and their involvement in purchase decisions of family and to analyze the women's involvement level/degree in these purchase decisions. Respondents (n=200) were surveyed on random basis through printed questionnaires by a personal interview during January 2010. Simple percentage method has been used to evaluate the data. Chi Square Test of Independence and Kolmogorov-Smirnov One Sample test has been applied to test the hypothesis. Study states a significant relationship between various demographic and geographic variables of women and their involvement in making purchase decisions of family except only one variable i.e. income. Study depicts a high degree of involvement of women in purchase decision making of the family. Study also delineates that majority of women are quality and brand conscious and most of them collect the information while making purchase decisions. This study furnishes information about women's demographic and geographic variables, their preference while making purchase decisions and relationship between various demographic and geographic variables of women and their involvement in making purchase decisions of the family. This study was confined to selected region of Pune district of Maharashtra with few randomly selected women respondents.

Keywords:

Purchase decisions, customer preference, demographic and geographic variables, Pune.

INTRODUCTION

Women are integral part of our society. A country like India, whose population of women alone is more than the total population of many countries. A few years ago, Indian society was male dominated while women were involved in only managing home; fulfilling the need of family members in terms of tasty and healthy food, neat and clean clothes etc. The last decade has witnessed a substantial change in the role of women in Indian society. The dependence of Indian economy is shifting towards activities unrelated to physical strength. Due to this shift, women are now capable of performing most economic task. Indian societies are also experiencing a change in cultural norms and ideas related to men's and women's task. Traditional role of men and women in society has been merged. Women are increasingly performing task traditionally assigned to men and vice versa. In addition, women are also getting greater autonomy, thereby no longer being dependent upon men for economic and social support and recognition. Due to these changes, women's roles have a major impact upon performance of task with in society. Major shift in societal role shows a reflection in family purchase decisions. Now scenario has been changed due to increase in literacy rate and working women forces. Therefore role of women has been also changed in the family. Now women not only manage the home successfully but also take part in making purchase decisions of family.

This study analyzes the relationship between demographic variables of women and their involvement in purchase decisions of family and it also examine the degree of involvement of women in these decisions.

REVIEW OF LITRATURE

Green and Cunningham (1975) compared family decision-making patterns under different conditions of female role perception. Their findings suggest differences between contemporary and traditional families, particularly within age and income categories. Purchasing involvement is related to sex, education, income, and stage of the family life cycle (Slama and Tashchian, 1985). William J. Qualls (1987) examined the impact of sex role orientation on the outcome of a family home purchase decisions and found a relatively strong relationship between sex role orientation and the degree of house hold influence, preference agreement mode of conflict resolution, and decision outcome. Furthermore, it is also found that household decision behavior is better explained in the context of a theoretical network of systematic house hold relationship rather than through a series of bivariate family relationship.

Cynthia Webster (1994) revealed a significant positive relationship between ethnic identification and husband dominance in decision making. However, because ethnic identification and product class interact with role specialization and

3) EDUCATION AND INVOLVEMENT IN PURCHASE DECISIONS

Table 3.1 delineates the relationship between education of women and their involvement in purchase decisions of the family. Majority of women who were postgraduate (28%) had high involvement, majority of them who were graduate (11.5%) had medium involvement and majority of them whose education was 10th to 12th standard (5.5%) had low

involvement. Table 3.2 delineates chi square calculated is 63.06 at 5% of level of significance and 8 degree of freedom which is much greater than tabulated value i.e. 15.507. Therefore hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between education of women and their involvement in purchase decisions of family is rejected.

Table 3.1: Cross Tabulation of education of women and their involvement in Purchase Decisions

Education	High		Medium		Low		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Illiterate	3	1.5	8	4.0	2	1.0	13	6.5
< 10 th	4	2.0	19	9.5	7	3.5	30	15
10 th -12 th	8	4.0	15	7.5	11	5.5	34	17
Graduation	24	12.0	23	11.5	4	2.0	51	25.5
Post Graduation	56	28.0	16	8.0	0	0.0	72	36
Total	95	47.5	81	40.5	24	12	200	100

Table 3.2: Chi Square Test of Independence

Chi Square Calculated	df	Level of significance	Chi Square Tabulated
63.06	8	5%	15.507

4) WORKING NATURE AND INVOLVEMENT IN PURCHASE DECISIONS

Table 4.1 delineates the relationship between working nature of women and their involvement in purchase decisions of the family. Majority of women who were working (26%) had high involvement, majority of them who were working (22%) had medium involvement and majority of them who were not working (9%) had low

involvement. Table 4.2 delineates chi square calculated is 7.38 at 5% of level of significance and 2 degree of freedom which is greater than tabulated value i.e. 5.991. Therefore hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between working nature of women and their involvement in purchase decisions of family is rejected.

Table 4.1: Cross Tabulation of working nature of women and their involvement in Purchase Decisions

Working Nature	High		Medium		Low		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Yes	52	26	44	22	6	3	102	51
No	43	21.5	37	18.5	18	9	98	49
Total	95	47.5	81	40.5	24	12	200	100

Table 4.2: Chi Square Test of Independence

Chi Square Calculated	df	Level of significance	Chi Square Tabulated
7.38	2	5%	5.991

5) OCCUPATION AND INVOLVEMENT IN PURCHASE DECISIONS

Table 5.1 delineates the relationship between occupation status of women and their involvement in purchase decisions of the family. Majority of women who were salaried (18.5%) had high involvement, majority of them who were house wife (14.5%) had medium involvement and majority of them who were students (4%) had low involvement. Table 5.2 delineates

chi square calculated is 31.067 at 5% of level of significance and 8 degree of freedom which is greater than tabulated value i.e. 15.987. Therefore hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between occupation status of women and their involvement in purchase decisions of family is rejected.

Table 5.1: Cross Tabulation of occupation status of women and their involvement in Purchase Decisions

Occupation	High		Medium		Low		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Students	11	5.5	18	9	8	4	37	18.5
Salaried	37	18.5	15	7.5	4	2	56	28
Own Business	29	14.5	14	7	3	1.5	46	23
House Wife	18	9	29	14.5	6	3	53	26.5
Others	0	0	5	2.5	3	1.5	8	4
Total	95	47.5	81	40.5	24	12	200	100

Table 5.2: Chi Square Test of Independence

Chi Square Calculated	df	Level of significance	Chi Square Tabulated
31.067	8	5%	15.987

6) MARITAL STATUS AND INVOLVEMENT IN PURCHASE DECISIONS

Table 6.1 delineates the relationship between marital status of women and their involvement in purchase decisions of the family. Majority of women who were married (36%) had high involvement, majority of them who were married (24.5%) had medium involvement and majority of them who were married (7.5%) had low

involvement. Table 6.2 delineates chi square calculated is 12.798 at 5% of level of significance and 2 degree of freedom, which is much greater than tabulated value i.e. 5.991. Therefore hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between marital status of women and their involvement in purchase decisions of family is rejected.

Table 6.1: Cross Tabulation of marital status of women and their involvement in Purchase Decisions

Marital Status	High		Medium		Low		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Single	23	11.5	32	16	9	4.5	84	42
Married	72	36	49	24.5	15	7.5	116	58
Total	95	47.5	81	40.5	24	12	200	100

Table 6.2: Chi Square Test of Independence

Chi Square Calculated	df	Level of significance	Chi Square Tabulated
12.798	2	5%	5.991

relative influence in decision making, generalizations cannot be made about Hispanic marital roles in the decision-making process. Furthermore, the effect of ethnic identification on marital roles in decision making interacts with the phase of purchase decision process. Kang and Kim (1998) examined the decision-making patterns for purchasing social clothes of three major Asian American consumer groups (Chinese, Japanese, and Korean). Results showed that the three groups display distinct reference group influence, media influence, and store attribute importance and that these patterns differ depending on the level of acculturation. The findings also suggested implications for various marketing and advertising strategies aimed at the three Asian American consumer markets.

Customer purchase decisions are affected by customer satisfaction (Gerpott *et al.*, 2001). A significant relationship is found between the involvement and brand loyalty in grocery market, by Knox and Walker, (2003). Singh and Kaur (2006) studied children's role in purchase decisions of the family and found that children in India have not much purchasing power in comparison of western counterpart. Still children in India not only influence market in terms of parental decisions but also represent themselves as future customers. Significant influences of demographic variables like age, occupation, family income are noticed in case of selection of products (Parmar and Gupta, 2007).

Rajesh Sud, (2007) found that the family structure in India has changed considerably in the last two decades. Nuclear families are replacing joint family. There is an increase in literacy rate of women and working women forces. Now parent centered families has been changed in child centered families. Hence the role of children in family decision making is increasing. Kotwal *et al.* (2008) pointed out that adolescent girls, influence of friends, and peers are the main cause for purchasing clothing items. Pathak and Tripathi (2009) argued that Indian customers have become more sensitive to quality, customer services and status.

The review of literature discussed above provides a deep insight of the work done by experts and researchers on some aspects of purchase decisions. However, lots of studies have been done to analyze women's role in family purchase decisions but in foreign context. Therefore present study was taken in Indian context.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

1. To study the various demographic and geographic variables of women.
2. To study the preference of women while making purchase decisions.
3. To analyze the relationship between demographic and geographic variables of women and their involvement in purchase decisions of family.
4. To analyze the women's involvement level in purchase decisions of family.

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

- There is no significant relationship between demographic and geographic variables of women and their involvement in purchase decisions of family.
- There is no significant difference in level of involvement of women in purchase decisions of family.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

DATA SOURCE

The study was based on both primary and secondary data. Secondary data was accumulated from books, journals, websites and other published sources available in Pune and it helped to formulate hypothesis, questionnaire, and review of literature. Utilizing the information from the secondary data, a structured questionnaire was prepared for women to accumulate the primary data, comprising open and closed ended questions. This questionnaire was tested by conducting a pilot study of randomly selected few women respondents. Utilizing the insight from pilot study, questionnaire was modified for the final study. Both Descriptive and exploratory research were used in compiling this study. While exploratory research helped in developing the hypothesis through the analysis of secondary data, descriptive research was used in order to complete this whole study. Survey method was employed to carry out this study through printed questionnaires by personal interview technique. Nominal

and Ordinal scales are utilized to take the response of respondents. Location of Research was Pune district of Maharashtra state. Simple percentage method has been used to analyze the demographic and geographic variables of respondents. Chi Square Test of Independence is applied to find out relationship between demographic and geographic variables of women and their involvement in purchase decisions of family. Kolmogorov-Smirnov One Sample test has been applied to know degree of involvement of women in purchase decisions of family. Cross tabulation has been utilized to represent the responses of respondents.

SAMPLING PLAN

Women respondents were selected on random basis from shopping malls, multiplexes, and academic institutions when they visited these on week days. The questionnaires were distributed simultaneously among 200 respondents during January 2010. Survey was done in all seven days. For the purpose of this survey, Random Sampling of Probability Sampling Technique has been employed as it gives every unit of the population a known and non-zero probability of being selected.

LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

- Study was limited to a few women selected on random basis.
- Frauds/fault in giving the right information can not be neglected.

➤ Due to short of time and resources study was confined to only a selected region of Pune district.

ANALYSIS, INTERPRETATION AND FINDINGS:

The Study is divided into two main headings according to hypothesis-

a) ANALYSIS OF RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN DEMOGRAPHIC & GEOGRAPHIC VARIABLES OF WOMEN AND THEIR INVOLVEMENT IN PURCHASE DECISIONS OF THE FAMILY

1) AGE GROUP AND INVOLVEMENT IN PURCHASE DECISIONS: Table 1.1 delineates the relationship between age group of women and their involvement in purchase

decisions of the family. Majority of women who belonged to age group 36-45 years (14%) had high involvement, majority of them who belonged to age group of 18-25 years (11.5%) had medium involvement and majority of them who belonged to age group of below 18 years and 46-55 years (3.5%) had low involvement. Table 1.2 delineates chi square calculated is 54.191 at 5% of level of significance and 10 degree of freedom which is much greater than tabulated value i.e. 18.307. Therefore hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between age group of women and their involvement in purchase decisions of family is rejected.

Table 1.1: Cross Tabulation of Age group of women and their involvement in Purchase Decisions

Age (Years)	High		Medium		Low		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
< 18	1	0.5	4	2.0	7	3.5	12	6
18-25	21	10.5	23	11.5	3	1.5	47	23.5
26-35	27	13.5	12	6.0	1	0.5	40	20
36-45	28	14.0	13	6.5	2	1.0	43	21
46-55	15	7.5	13	6.5	7	3.5	35	17.5
> 55	3	1.5	16	8.0	4	2.0	23	11.5
Total	95	47.5	81	40.5	24	12.0	200	100

Table 1.2: Chi Square Test of Independence

Chi Square Calculated	df	Level of significance	Chi Square Tabulated
54.191	10	5%	18.307

2) RESIDING AREA AND INVOLVEMENT IN PURCHASE DECISIONS

Table 2.1 delineates the relationship between residing area of women and their involvement in purchase decisions of the family. Majority of women who resided in urban area (34%) had high involvement, majority of them who resided in urban area (25.5%) had medium involvement and majority of them who resided in rural area (9.5%) had low involvement. Table 2.2

delineates chi square calculated is 20.995 at 5% of level of significance and 2 degree of freedom which is much greater than tabulated value i.e. 5.991. Therefore hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between residing area of women and their involvement in purchase decisions of family is rejected.

Table 2.1: Cross Tabulation of residing area of women and their involvement in Purchase Decisions

Area	High		Medium		Low		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Urban	68	34.0	51	25.5	5	2.5	124	62
Rural	27	13.5	30	15.0	19	9.5	76	38
Total	95	47.5	81	40.5	24	12.0	200	100

Table 2.2: Chi Square Test of Independence

Chi Square Calculated	df	Level of significance	Chi Square Tabulated
20.995	2	5%	5.991

7) INCOMES AND INVOLVEMENT IN PURCHASE DECISIONS

Table 7.1 delineates the relationship between incomes of women and their involvement in purchase decisions of the family. Majority of women whose monthly income was 21000-30000 (8%) had high involvement, majority of them whose monthly income was 5000-10000 (4.5%) had medium involvement and majority of them whose monthly income was below

5000 (2%) had low involvement. Table 7.2 delineates chi square calculated is 7.179 at 5% of level of significance and 10 degree of freedom which is much less than tabulated value i.e. 18.307. Therefore hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between income of women and their involvement in purchase decisions of family is accepted.

Table 7.1: Cross Tabulation of income of women and their involvement in Purchase Decisions

Income (Monthly)	High		Medium		Low		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
< 5000	8	4	7	3.5	4	2	19	9.5
5000-10000	12	6	9	4.5	3	1.5	24	12
11000-15000	9	4.5	6	3	2	1	17	8.5
16000-20000	5	2.5	4	2	2	1	11	5.5
21000-30000	16	8	5	2.5	1	0.5	22	11
> 30000	6	3	3	1.5	0	0	9	4.5
Total	56	28	34	17	12	6	102	51

Table 7.2: Chi Square Test of Independence

Chi Square Calculated	df	Level of significance	Chi Square Tabulated
7.179	10	5%	18.307

8) TYPE OF FAMILY AND INVOLVEMENT IN PURCHASE DECISIONS

Table 8.1 delineates the relationship between family type of women and their involvement in purchase decisions of the family. Majority of women who belonged to nuclear family (38%) had high involvement, majority of them who belonged to nuclear family (24.5%) had medium involvement and majority of them who belonged to nuclear family (8%) had low involvement.

Table 8.2 delineates chi square calculated is 8.191 at 5% of level of significance and 2 degree of freedom which is greater than tabulated value i.e. 5.991. Therefore hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between family type of women and their involvement in purchase decisions of family is rejected.

Table 8.1: Cross Tabulation of family type of women and their involvement in Purchase Decisions

Family Type	High		Medium		Low		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Nuclear	76	38	49	24.5	16	8	141	70.5
Joint	19	9.5	32	16	8	4	59	29.5
Total	95	47.5	81	40.5	24	12	200	100

Table 8.2: Chi Square Test of Independence

Chi Square Calculated	df	Level of significance	Chi Square Tabulated
8.191	2	5%	5.991

9) SIZE OF FAMILY AND INVOLVEMENT IN PURCHASE DECISIONS

Table 9.1 delineates the relationship between family size of women and their involvement in purchase decisions of the family. Majority of women who belonged to family of size 4-5 members (19.5%) had high involvement, majority of them who belonged to family of size 4-5 and 6-7 members (16%) had medium involvement and majority of them who belonged to

family of size 4- 5 (6%) had low involvement. Table 8.2 delineates chi square calculated is 21.141 at 5% of level of significance and 6 degree of freedom which is much greater than tabulated value i.e. 12.592. Therefore hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between family size of women and their involvement in purchase decisions of family is rejected.

Table 9.1: Cross Tabulation of family size of women and their involvement in Purchase Decisions

Family Size	High		Medium		Low		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
2 to 3	28	14	8	8	2	1	38	19
4 to 5	39	19.5	32	16	12	6	83	41.5
6 to 7	16	8	32	16	5	2.5	53	26.5
> 7	12	6	9	4.5	5	2.5	26	13
Total	95	47.5	81	40.5	24	12	200	100

Table 9.2: Chi Square Test of Independence

Chi Square Calculated	df	Level of significance	Chi Square Tabulated
21.141	6	5%	12.592

10) INFORMATION COLLECTION DECISION AND INVOLVEMENT IN PURCHASE DECISIONS

Table 10.1 delineates the relationship between information collection decision of women and their involvement in purchase decisions of the family. Majority of women who collected information while purchase making decision (43%) had high involvement, majority of them who collected information (32.5%) had medium involvement and majority of them who did not collect information (9%) had low

involvement. Table 10.2 delineates chi square calculated is 48.989 at 5% of level of significance and 2 degree of freedom, which is much greater than tabulated value i.e. 5.991. Therefore hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between information collection decision of women and their involvement in purchase decisions of family is rejected.

Table 10.1: Cross Tabulation of information collection decision of women and their involvement in Purchase Decisions

Information Collection	High		Medium		Low		Total	
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Yes	86	43	65	32.5	6	3	157	78.5
No	9	4.5	16	8	18	9	43	21.5
Total	95	47.5	81	40.5	24	12	200	100

Table 10.2: Chi Square Test of Independence

Chi Square Calculated	df	Level of significance	Chi Square Tabulated
48.989	2	5%	5.991

11) PREFERENTIAL ANALYSIS OF WOMEN

Table 11.1 delineates majority of women (40.5%) were quality conscious, majority of them (30%) were brand conscious and other majority (29.5%) were interested in price, discounts, schemes and others.

Preference	Brand		Quality		Price		Discount/Schemes		Others		Total
	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	No.
1 st	60	30	81	40.5	26	13	19	9.5	14	7	200
2 nd	52	26	48	24	57	28.5	26	13	17	8.5	200
3 rd	37	18.5	32	16	68	34	41	20.5	22	11	200
4 th	32	16	23	11.5	27	13.5	51	25.5	62	31	200
5 th	19	9.5	16	8	22	11	63	31.5	85	42.5	200
Total	200	100	200	100	200	100	200	100	200	100	1000

B) ANALYSIS TO FINDOUT THE DEGREE OF INVOLVEMENT OF WOMEN IN PURCHASE DECISIONS OF THE FAMILY

To analyze the degree of involvement of women in making purchase decisions of family, responses has been taken on ordinal scale ranging from high involvement to low involvement. To find out the degree of involvement between a set of value observed and values specified by the null hypothesis, Kolmogorov-Smirnov One Sample Test has been applied. From the

table 12.1 we find that the largest absolute difference is 0.214, which is known as the calculated Kolmogorov-Smirnov D Value. The critical value of D at an alpha of 5% is 0.096. As the calculated D exceeds the critical value of 0.096, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the level of involvement of women in purchase decisions of family is rejected.

Table 12.1: Tabulation of Kolmogorov-Smirnov D Value

Involvement in Purchase Decisions	Observed Number	Observed Proportion	Observed Cumulative Proportion	Null Proportion	Null Cumulative Proportion	Absolute Difference Observed & Null
High	95	0.475	0.475	0.3333	0.333	0.142
Medium	81	0.405	0.880	0.3333	0.666	0.214
Low	24	0.120	1.000	0.3333	1.000	0.000

CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

Study states a significant relationship between various demographic and geographic variables of women and their involvement in making purchase decisions of family except only one variable: income. Study depicts a high degree of involvement of women in purchase decision making of the family. We could also find out that majority of women are quality and brand conscious and most of them collect the information while making purchase decisions. We also noticed an increase in literacy level and working nature of women.

Now women are contributing good amount to the house hold income. This study furnishes information about women's demographic and geographic variables, their preference while making purchase decisions and relationship between various demographic and geographic variables of women and their involvement in making purchase decisions of the family. The study will further prove to be great help to the researchers/management students who want to do similar or related study in the future.

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Kohinoor Business School

Center for Management Research, Khandala

Kohinoor Global Campus, Sub Division B, Old Pune-Mumbai Highway, Khandala - 410 301,

Dist - Pune, Maharashtra, India Tel : (02114) 269018 / 19/ 20 Fax : (02114) 269224

Email : kbsjournal@kohinoor.ac.in Website : www.kbscmr.kohinoor.ac.in